

Finite element simulation of fibre-reinforced polymers with realistic fibre orientation and fibre volume fraction distributions

O.V. Ferguson^{a,b,*}, L.P. Mikkelsen^{b,*}

^a*LM Wind Power, Jupitervej 6, Kolding, 6000, Denmark*

^b*Department of Wind Energy, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, 4000, Denmark*

Abstract

We introduce a software package for finite element simulation of continuous fibre-reinforced polymers, based on microstructural field quantities derived from two- and three-dimensional images. Optical microscopy and X-ray computed micro-tomography are employed to capture the fibre distribution, from which fibre orientation and fibre volume fractions are extracted. Field quantities are incorporated into a static compression finite element model implemented in AbaqusTM. The approach enables the simulation of composites containing local imperfections. Results highlight that combined variations in fibre orientation and fibre volume fraction can induce stress and strain localisation, emphasising the importance of realistic fibre distributions when investigating material behaviour.

Keywords: Structure tensor method, Stress-strain distribution, Virtual testing

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: olen@dtu.dk (O.V. Ferguson), lapm@dtu.dk (L.P. Mikkelsen)

1. Code metadata

Nr.	Code metadata description	Please fill in this column
C1	Current code version	V01.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	2D optical microscopy model 3D X-ray μ CT model
C3	Permanent link to reproducible capsule	2D capsule 3D capsule
C4	Legal code license	MIT License (MIT)
C5	Code versioning system used	Git
C6	Software code languages, tools and services used	Python, Linux, Fortran
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Microsoft Windows, Linux
C8	If available, link to developer documentation/manual	
C9	Support email for questions	olen@dtu.dk

2. Introduction

2.1. Motivation

The stress-strain analysis of fibre-reinforced composites is often simplified to layers of straight fibres with predefined orientations and a specific fibre volume fraction, V_f . This assumption, however, overlooks the impact of local imperfections, such as fibre misalignments and resin-rich regions, which can significantly alter the stress-strain distribution within the composite material. Local stress concentrations from imperfections can ultimately impact material performance and cause a significant reduction in strength. This is especially true for unidirectional composites loaded in compression, where Budiansky and Fleck [1] showed that fibre misalignments in carbon fibre-reinforced composites drastically reduce the compressive strength. Kyriakides

et al. [2] investigated the impact of variable fibre orientations coupled with local reductions in V_f on the compressive strength. Their method was based on an idealised micro-mechanical model and does not consider realistic fibre distributions. However, compared to a constant V_f model, a reduction in the initial stiffness and compressive strength was observed. Wilhelmsson et al. [3] developed an approach to model compressive behaviour based on realistic fibre orientation distributions. This method was demonstrated for a non-crimp fabric, where the orientation distribution is quantified from optical microscopy images. However, the method does not quantify the V_f distribution but estimates the strength based on orientation data alone.

2.2. Implementation

We present a method for quantifying the fibre orientation and fibre volume fraction distribution for continuous fibre-reinforced polymers based on 2D and 3D images acquired using optical microscopy and X-ray computed micro-tomography, respectively. The distributions are used in a Finite Element (FE) model to simulate the stress-strain behaviour for a given load scenario. The method is demonstrated for a carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profile used in [4] and is presented in a Code Ocean Notebook. The commercial FE software, AbaqusTM, is used to model the material behaviour when subjected to compressive loading. The complete version of the software is available in a GitHub repository, where some parts of the code require an AbaqusTM license to run.

Figure 1 presents a general overview of the method, which consists of four major steps. The first step in Figure 1a presents the acquired image from either imaging modality, where fibres appear white, and the matrix material appears dark grey. The second step, presented in Figure 1b, determines the distribution of the field quantities, fibre orientation, ϕ_{xy} , and fibre volume fraction, V_f . Like the work presented by Jeppesen et al. [5], fibre orientations are determined using the structure tensor method. The method yields a vector field describing the dominant material orientations in the image, which may be used for estimating the fibre orientation distribu-

tion. The V_f distribution is determined using a three-phase segmentation procedure

Figure 1: Method workflow from image acquisition to finite element simulation based on realistic fibre distributions. FE-simulation results in (d) are based on a compression load case, with an axial displacement applied in the x-direction corresponding to $\epsilon_x = 1\%$.

and the areal method presented by Cann et al. [6]. The method is based on local averaging of fibre, matrix and boundary pixels using a mean filter, where the image quality and number of dimensions for the chosen imaging modality govern the accuracy. The third step, presented in Figure 1c, maps the field quantities determined from the image to a FE-model. First, the FE-model is generated based on the image's dimensions, followed by the generation of a mesh where integration points are extracted and superimposed onto the image data. The respective field quantities are then mapped to the integration points and imported into the FE-model in AbaqusTM. Material properties are updated locally based on the V_f distribution, and local material coordinate systems are rotated according to the fibre orientation distribution. Finally, with the material properties updated in the FE-model, a static compression simulation is executed in AbaqusTM. Figure 1d presents the resulting strain distribution when the material is loaded in compression with a displacement corresponding to $\varepsilon_x = 1\%$. The shear strain distribution, ε_{12} , is plotted using integration point values extracted from the FE-model. From this, localised shear strains are associated with local variations in the fibre structure of the composite material.

3. Impact overview

Results presented for this method are based on static compression of a rectangular/cuboid component. However, the method can be applied to any loading conditions and desired geometry. It can thus be beneficial for studying complex geometries where fibre orientation and fibre volume fraction distributions are essential for the structural behaviour.

The software presented here is used to study the stress-strain distribution resulting from realistic fibre distributions. The method can, however, be coupled with damage models used for simulating different failure modes and associated failure strengths. The approach has been used to predict the compressive strength of fibre-reinforced composites based on image data from different imaging modalities [7]. The study is based on X-ray computed micro-tomography and optical microscopy images of a sim-

ilar material to the one presented here, where we compare the accuracy of model predictions for 3D and 2D fibre distributions, respectively. By accounting for both field quantities in the image data, we get more accurate predictions for the local material behaviour when subjected to compressive loading. Like the conclusion in [2], it is shown that a variable V_f distribution relative to a case with constant V_f yields lower compressive stiffness and strength predictions [7].

The method has been demonstrated for a pristine material system with typical fibre orientation and V_f distributions. Still, it can also be used to study the detrimental effect of more complex fibre orientation distributions. This is the case for manufacturing-induced defects in composite materials, where local imperfections may cause severe restructuring of the fibre architecture. As manufacturing-induced defects come in many different shapes and sizes, this method can assess the severity of a range of defects and identify potential risks. Similarly, this method can be used as a tool for quality assessment in line with the manufacturing of fibre-reinforced polymer components.

4. Future work and updates

The method presented in this paper is intended to investigate the compressive strength associated with manufacturing-induced defects in carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles. The outcome will greatly improve the understanding of fibre misalignment defects and help define a mitigation strategy to avoid detrimental effects on the structural performance.

5. Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

6. Acknowledgments

This work was funded by grant no. 1044-00124B from the Innovation Fund Denmark.

References

- [1] B. Budiansky, N. Fleck, Compressive failure of fibre composites, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 41 (1993) 183–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096\(93\)90068-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096(93)90068-Q).
- [2] S. Kyriakides, R. Arseculeratne, E. Perry, K. Liechti, On the compressive failure of fiber reinforced composites, *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 32 (1995) 689–738. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7683\(94\)00157-R](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7683(94)00157-R), time Dependent Problems in Mechanics.
- [3] D. Wilhelmsson, R. Talreja, R. Gutkin, L. E. Asp, Compressive strength assessment of fibre composites based on a defect severity model, *Composites Science and Technology* 181 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2019.107685>.
- [4] O. V. Ferguson, L. P. Mikkelsen, Three-dimensional finite element modeling of anisotropic materials using X-ray computed micro-tomography data, *Software Impacts* 17 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpa.2023.100523>.
- [5] N. Jeppesen, V. A. Dahl, A. N. Christensen, A. B. Dahl, L. P. Mikkelsen, Characterization of the fiber orientations in non-crimp glass fiber reinforced composites using structure tensor, in: *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, volume 942, IOP Publishing Ltd, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/942/1/012037>.
- [6] M. T. Cann, D. O. Adams, C. L. Schneider, Characterization of fiber volume fraction gradients in composite laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials* 42 (2008) 447–466. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998307086206>.

- [7] O. V. Ferguson, J. B. Jørgensen, L. P. Mikkelsen, Compressive strength predictions for carbon fibre-reinforced pultruded profiles: Imaging modalities for quantifying the detrimental effect of fibre misalignments (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17037149>, submitted for review [preprint].